

A European survey

Inclusion4EU

Existing Competencies in the Teaching of Inclusive Design in Informatics programmes

Research report

Inclusion
4EU

EXISTING COMPETENCIES IN THE TEACHING OF INCLUSIVE DESIGN IN INFORMATICS PROGRAMMES

A EUROPEAN SURVEY

Inclusion4EU Consortium, 2024

Recommended citation: Recommended citation:

The Inclusion4EU Consortium, Existing Competencies in the Teaching of Inclusive Design in Informatics Programmes. A European Survey. 2024. Available at: <https://ascnet.ie/inclusion4eu-website/research/>

Inclusion4EU, an Erasmus+ project, investigates Co-Design as a method to make software development processes more inclusive, starting with the education of future Computer Science professionals. It researches co-design methodologies in European universities, develops open-access teaching resources, collaborates with marginalized groups to co-design inclusive software practices, and provides training courses for teachers. The project partners are Technological University Dublin, Mälardalen University, Télécom SudParis, Informatics Europe, and SAP.

INFORMATICS
EUROPE

Inclusion4EU: Co-Design for Inclusion in Software Development Design
Grant Agreement: 2022-1-IE02-KA220-HED-000085653

This project has been funded with support from the European Commission. This publication reflects the views only of the author, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

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1. Executive Summary

Designing software systems that are inclusive of as wide a range of users as possible is an ethical, legal and economic imperative. To make software systems inclusive requires novel approaches to the software design process, including looking at new models and methodologies, such as Accessibility, Universal Design, Participatory Design and Co-Design. These techniques can be incorporated into existing approaches for developers in the IT industry, but to help ensure all new developers are aware of these techniques, this research will develop new teaching and assessment materials to aid in the teaching of inclusive design in third-level institutions.

The Inclusion4EU project is targeted at third level educators, and specifically those that deliver Computer Science and related disciplines programmes. Inclusion4EU is developing new modules, learning resources and a virtual Community of Practice in Inclusive design for Computer Science faculties. The project follows a “train the trainer” model for up-skilling Computer Science educators in the delivery of Inclusive design across Europe.

This report is one of the milestone outputs of the Inclusion4EU project. It presents results obtained from a survey conducted in from late 2023 to early 2024 that polled educators from Computer Science and related disciplines on teaching practices in Inclusive design across Europe. The survey was completed by respondents from 35 universities across 22 European countries. Participants were surveyed on whether Inclusive design is taught to Computer Science students at each institution, the reasons why Inclusive design is or is not taught, how Inclusive design is taught (for example, as a standalone course or embedded within other courses), the background of staff who teach Inclusive design and the scope of Inclusive design curricula. Data was also gathered on teaching and learning methods used (theory, case studies, practical work) and how Inclusive design is assessed. The results of the survey are a comprehensive insight into teaching practices for Inclusive design in Computer Science and related disciplines and will inform the development of new curricula and learning resources for Inclusive design as part of the Inclusion4EU project. Some of the important findings that emerged from the survey include:

- Half of the institutions surveyed teach Inclusive design as part of Computer Science or related programmes, however half do not.
- There is widespread agreement about the importance of teaching Inclusive design to students enrolled in Computer Science or related programmes. This importance was

noted whether an institute taught Inclusive design as part of their Computer Science or related programmes.

- When Inclusive design is not taught as part of Computer Science or related programmes, the most common reasons given include the view that the programmes are already too busy (other subjects are prioritised), and this topic has not been considered.
- Most institutions devote a relatively small number of hours to teaching Inclusive design in their Computer Science or related programmes, 80% of institutions surveyed teach 10 hours or less per semester.
- Inclusive design is primarily taught in Computer Science or related courses that focus on Web and Information Systems, Database Systems, Information Retrieval and Digital Libraries, Data Fusion.
- Inclusive design is the least commonly taught in Computer Science or related courses that focus on Cryptology, Security, Privacy, Quantum Crypto.

2. The Inclusion4EU project

The Inclusion4EU project (www.inclusion4eu.eu) is firmly rooted in improving inclusion and diversity in education. Specifically, it aims to improve Computer Science lectures and students' understanding of Inclusive Design. This includes an understanding of both poor and best practice and as the project aims to equip lecturers with skills, tools and materials to incorporate best practices in human-centered Inclusive design.

We are hopeful this work will stimulate innovative learning and teaching practice by equipping Computer Science lecturers with improved knowledge of how to run human-centered inclusive design sessions. Inclusion4EU is developing tools and resources for Inclusive Design by applying co-design methodologies, providing practical guidance for Computer Science lecturers about how to involve end users in software design, development and evaluation. The developed resources will allow academics to facilitate co-design as part of their teaching, and industry professionals to employ the methodology as part of professional practice. The approach is an example of research-based learning where co-design is an innovative pedagogical approach covering multiple disciplines. It incorporates key tenets of inclusion including sustainability, social responsibility and ethics. It aims to building inclusive higher education systems by increasing access and participation by including people from a wide background who are often not considered in software design (e.g., older people or people with physical, sensory or cognitive impairments).

Inclusion4EU has implemented several co-design sessions involving participants academics, industry practitioners, students, and community services members, fostering civic engagement and promoting both formal and informal learning for all participants. The sessions contributed to the creation of a rich shared understanding of human-centered design, digital inclusion and accessibility, one that students would not otherwise experience through traditional book-based learning.

The timing of this work is crucial. Society is increasingly technology driven with new developments precipitated by Covid-19. Technologies such as AI are becoming mainstream. We live in the shadow of technology scandals that have not properly considered the consequences and impacts of technology on end users. Now is the time to consider new practices for truly inclusive design that ensure no users are left behind, further marginalised or negatively impacted.

This project builds on the exceptional success of the consortium in delivering the Erasmus+ funded Ethics4EU project (www.ethics4eu.eu) that developed a rich repository of curricula for Computer Science lecturers to teach digital ethics. The work of Inclusion4EU is a natural extension of Ethics4EU – building repositories, tools and expertise to promote truly inclusive design practices.

3. Survey Description

One of the aims of Inclusion4EU is to better understand the current landscape of Inclusive Design teaching in Computer Science Higher Education Institutions across Europe. It is of central importance to the project to understand if and how Inclusive Design is currently taught in Computer Science programmes, the background of the teaching staff, the scope of the curricula, the teaching practices and learning methods, assessment and learning outcomes.

Our study started in September 2023 when Technological University Dublin (TU Dublin) together with Informatics Europe, Institut Mines-Télécom, and Mälardalen University, developed the first draft of an online questionnaire. Before the survey was launched, it was pre-tested on a small sample of respondents from Inclusion4EU partner institutions, feedback on improving the questionnaire was incorporated, leading to its final version.

In November 2023, the online questionnaire was sent to all members and networking partners of Informatics Europe reaching over 150 European Universities from more than 30 European countries. It was also publicly available from the Informatics Europe website. The data collection continued until the end of February. To get more survey responses, two weeks before the end of the fieldwork, reminders were sent to all previously contacted European Universities. In addition, the survey invitation was shared on a range of social media platforms, including X (former Twitter) and relevant LinkedIn groups. Participants did not receive any incentives or remuneration to complete the survey.

The survey was structured in three parts. The first part consisted of demographic questions (Section A) answered by all 48 respondents. The rest of the questionnaire was split into two parts based on whether the respondent's institution teaches Inclusive Design as part of any Computer Science or related programmes. The second part (Section B) was addressed only to those that replied that their institutions do not teach Inclusive Design as part of any Computer Science or related programmes, 24 out of 48 respondents. The third part (Section C) was completed by the 24 participants who responded that their institutions teach Inclusive Design as part of any Computer Science or related programmes. Below we present the results of the survey according to this structure, including all the detailed questions, statistics and qualitative answers.

4. Analysis of Answers

We received 48 valid responses to our survey.

Twenty-three countries were represented among the 48 respondents that took part in this survey. It is worth noting that the majority of the EU member countries are represented, as well as several other European countries. The majority (near 32%) of the respondents are from institutions in Spain, which most probably resulted from strongly connected Spanish networks of Informatics Europe. To assure that the Spanish answers did not bias the results all subsequent questions were carefully analyzed and steps were taken to balance the data using Jackknife resampling¹ whereby each response is systematically left out of the overall sample to ensure that no single response has a significant impact on the overall outcome. Additionally, pairs and trios of the responses from the Spanish institutions were left out to explore whether or not those responses had a significant impact on the overall trends, and it was found that they did not.

What country is your institution primarily based in?

Value ○ 1 ○ 4 ○ 10

Map: Inclusion4EU • Created with Datawrapper

¹Tukey, J. W. (1977). *Exploratory Data Analysis* (Vol. 2). Reading.

The survey represents a diverse range of **institution sizes**, with student populations ranging from 101 to over 10,000. Notably, the majority of institutions surveyed are large universities, with 71% enrolling more than 10,000 students. Additionally, nearly 80% of the institutions have over 500 students enrolled in Informatics and related programs.

46% of the respondents are from institutions that focus exclusively on technical subjects (e.g., technical universities, Institutes of Technology), whereas around 54% are from institutions that provide a broader range of content (e.g., traditional universities).

Of the 48 institutions surveyed, 3 of them exclusively teach Doctorate programmes, and 1 exclusively teaches undergraduate programmes, whereas the overwhelming majority teach a combination of all **levels**.

The majority of respondents hold teaching **roles**, with over 80% identifying as either Professors or Lecturers, both of which are full-time academic staff in Europe. Additionally, several respondents hold academic management roles, bringing valuable insights into resource allocation challenges, a key issue in teaching Inclusive Design in Computer Science programs. Respondents were allowed to select more than one role.

In the survey, we asked institutions whether or not they include Inclusive Design in their Computer Science or related programs.

Based on their responses, we then directed each institution to a tailored set of questions. Institutions that teach Inclusive Design were asked about how they integrate it, the methods they use, and the challenges they face. Meanwhile, those that do not teach Inclusive Design were prompted to provide reasons for its exclusion, including any barriers or considerations that have impacted their decision.

Notably, **the results revealed that 50% of respondents reported their institutions do not teach Inclusive Design, while the other 50% confirmed that they do.**

This balanced split offers critical insights into both the existing gaps and the progress being made in incorporating Inclusive Design into higher education curricula.

4.1 Institutions that are not teaching Inclusive Design in their Informatics programmes

Over 50% of the respondents from Institutions that are not teaching Inclusive Design in their Informatics programmes consider the teaching of Inclusive Designs as either being “Important” or “Very Important”.

How important do you think it is that Inclusive Design is taught in Informatics programmes?

Chart: Inclusion4EU • Created with Datawrapper

When asked to explain their ratings, **respondents provided a variety of reasons highlighting the importance of teaching Inclusive Design.** The most common reason was that it equips future technology professionals to develop applications that address diverse user needs, ensuring accessibility and inclusivity. Additionally, it helps them navigate ethical challenges and meet legal requirements. Respondents emphasized that Informatics professionals have an ethical duty to consider the societal impact of their work.

In terms of the delivery of content, some respondents felt that Inclusive Design should be taught by incorporating it into existing modules, whereas others felt it should be delivered once technical and design competencies were taught. Others suggested that it should only be a part of human-centric modules such as Human Computer Interaction. Some suggested

that the incorporation of a separate module either on inclusion itself or as part of a separate transferrable skills module on ethics would be a good solution.

Those who believed there was no need to teach Inclusive Design acknowledged its importance but felt it wasn't crucial for Informatics courses, or that these courses were already sufficiently accessible. Some viewed it as a "nice to have" addition, but only after core technology and design elements had been covered.

We explored the reasons **why Inclusive Design is not included in the respondents' institutions** by having them rate several statements. Participants assessed the extent to which various factors contribute to the absence of Inclusive Design in their Informatics programmes. The results reveal several key barriers:

- Approximately 35% of respondents perceive that the lack of importance attributed to Inclusive Design is a significant barrier to its teaching.
- More than 50% of respondents identified staff expertise as a critical issue.
- Similarly, over 50% noted that staff availability poses a challenge.
- A significant majority, 80%, reported that their programmes are too busy to incorporate Inclusive Design.
- One third (33.33%) of respondents believe that Inclusive Design is not relevant to the modules they teach.
- Additionally, one third (33.33%) indicated that funding is a concern.
- Finally, over 60% of respondents admitted they have never considered integrating Inclusive Design into their programmes.

To what extent do the following statements contribute to Inclusive Design not being taught in your institution?

Not at all
 Not much
 I'm not sure
 Somewhat
 Greatly

Inclusive Design is not perceived as important

We have a lack of staff expertise

We have a lack of staff availability

Programmes are already too busy (other subjects are prioritized)

Inclusive Design is not relevant to the subjects we teach

We are lacking the funds

We have never considered it

Chart: Inclusion4EU • Created with Datawrapper

Furthermore, respondents who said their institutions have no plans to teach Inclusive Design in Informatics programmes, indicated lack of staff with appropriate training, lack of interest, and lack of awareness of the need for a knowledge of Inclusive Design as main barriers to its teaching.

Only 8% of respondents stated that there were plans to teach Inclusive Design in Informatics programmes at their institution in the future, with one respondent noting that their institution had plans to pilot incorporating inclusive design as part of their software development course and an experimental project in 2024.

Are there plans to teach Inclusive Design in Informatics programmes at your institution in the future?

Chart: Inclusion4EU • Created with Datawrapper

In conclusion, while a significant majority of respondents recognize the importance of teaching Inclusive Design in Informatics programmes, numerous barriers prevent its implementation in their institutions. These barriers include perceptions of the topic's relevance, staff expertise and availability, and the overwhelming demands of existing curricula. Although many respondents acknowledge the ethical responsibility of Informatics professionals to consider the societal impact of their work, only a small percentage indicated plans to incorporate Inclusive Design into their programmes in the near future.

To address these challenges, enhancing education and awareness around Inclusive Design is crucial. Developing initiatives that can be integrated into existing courses, along with creating accessible teaching materials, will help elevate its importance. Promoting user diversity within the institution and fostering a culture of open dialogue about inclusion-related challenges are also vital.

Ultimately, addressing these issues will ensure that future technology professionals are equipped to meet the diverse needs of all users.

4.2 Institutions that are teaching Inclusive Design in their Informatics programmes

In institutions that are already teaching Inclusive design in Informatics, no one surveyed regarded the teaching of Inclusive design as unimportant, over 90% of the respondents rate the teaching of Inclusive design as either being “Important” or “Very Important”.

How important do you think it is that inclusive design is taught in Informatics programmes?

Chart: Inclusion4EU • Created with Datawrapper

Below the levels of education at which Inclusive Design is taught as part of Informatics or related programmes in surveyed institutions. The data highlights a greater emphasis on teaching Inclusive Design at the undergraduate and postgraduate levels compared to the doctorate level.

At which level of education is Inclusive Design taught as part of Informatics or related programmes in your institution?

Undergraduate / Bachelor (EQF 6)	19
Postgraduate / Master (EQF 7)	17
Doctorate (EQF 8)	8
I Don't Know	1

We investigated if Inclusion is being taught as a stand-alone module, or distributed throughout several modules, or a combination of both.

Please note that in this case, a “module” refers to a single topic that a student studies over one or two semesters, e.g. Databases, Computer Networks, etc.

Data reveals that 3 institutions offer it as a stand-alone module, while 8 institutions incorporate it threaded throughout several modules. Additionally, 6 institutions utilize a combination of both methods, and 7 institutions include Inclusive Design in one or more courses as a voluntary initiative of individual lecturers. Overall, the findings indicate a diverse range of strategies for integrating Inclusive Design into curricula, with a preference for incorporating it within multiple modules rather than as a standalone course.

How is Inclusive Design taught?

Chart: Inclusion4EU • Created with Datawrapper

People teaching Inclusive design come from a wide variety of backgrounds, with many coming from multiple disciplines. The most represented sub-discipline is Human Computer Interaction at 55%. However, some of those teaching Inclusive design have backgrounds in Philosophy, Psychology, and Ethnography.

What is the background of the people teaching Inclusive Design?

Chart: Inclusion4EU • Created with Datawrapper

When it comes to the involvement of **guest lecturers**, a significant majority would have a background in academia. With about a third from industry, 13% from professional bodies, and a smaller representation from community services at 3%.

Additionally, the **involvement of end users and organisations or associations supporting vulnerable groups** primarily manifests through invited guest lectures aimed at increasing awareness of Inclusive Design topics. Beyond lecturing, these organisations often collaborate with students, providing valuable advice on assessments and assisting in the development of more inclusive technology solutions. Furthermore, they play a role in evaluating assessments, ensuring that the learning outcomes are aligned with the principles of inclusivity.

The responses to **how many hours per semester an average student is exposed to Inclusive Design topics** revealed a wide range. Half of the respondents (50%) indicated that students are exposed to these topics for 1 to 5 hours per semester, while only 8.5% reported 20+ hours. This indicates substantial variation in how Inclusive Design is integrated into Informatics and related programmes. Furthermore, if 5 hours is considered "few," many students may receive minimal exposure to these important topics each semester.

How many hours per semester would you say is an average student exposed to Inclusive Design topics?

Chart: Inclusion4EU • Created with Datawrapper

We investigated the about perceptions of **whether students are exposed to the teaching of Inclusive Design sufficiently**. One-third (33%) of the participants responded they felt that there is not enough Inclusive design being taught in their institutions. Over 58% felt that enough Inclusive design is being taught “to a certain extent”. Only 4% percent of those surveyed believed that their intuitions are teaching enough Inclusive Design in their Informatics or related programmes.

Together, these two set of answers highlight a trend: while there is acknowledgment of the importance of Inclusive Design education, the actual implementation in terms of hours taught is notably limited. This mismatch suggests a gap between educational ideals and practices, calling for a reevaluation of how Inclusive Design is integrated into curricula.

How can the extent to which Inclusive Design is taught be improved? We asked participants to select from a number of possible options which would be more relevant to this purpose.

Do you think the following would improve the extent to which Inclusive Design is taught in your institution?

Chart: Inclusion4EU • Created with Datawrapper

Responses indicate that all of the factors suggested were felt to improve how Inclusive Design is taught to a significant degree, but the last two factors (*Collaboration with Disability Organisations* and *Assistive Technology*) were slightly less enthusiastically rated than the other factors.

We asked if there’s anything else that would help your institution intensify the teaching of Inclusive Design. The respondents provided a wide range of useful and interesting suggestions for enhancing this area of education. In terms of developing **teaching content** related to Inclusive Design, specific themes included creating materials on the importance of Inclusive Design, best practices, and case studies.

Additionally, they recommended producing various **teaching artifacts**, such as posters highlighting aspects of Inclusive Design like accessibility standards, inclusive language, and inclusive methodologies. Suggestions also included developing disability simulation tools and resources to educate students about ethnographic studies. Respondents emphasized the need for more **national competitions** and field trips in this area. For assessments, they proposed **iterative design assignments** that span multiple years and authentic assessment scenarios.

Interestingly, many respondents felt that integrating people with diverse needs into every aspect of the educational process is crucial. As one respondent stated: “Access to Higher Education for students, researchers, and lecturers with diverse needs.” Their suggestions included having individuals with diverse needs, along with staff from disability services, work with students to create more accessible **assessments**.

Some respondents suggested including a dedicated **final-year module on Inclusive Design**, while others believed that mainstream diversity **training for staff** and management could be key to encouraging inclusion.

Although Inclusive Design may not be taught sufficiently, it is valuable to examine the methods through which it is being taught. We asked our respondents “**How frequently are the following teaching methods used to teach Inclusive Design?**”

Data shows clearly that traditional approaches to teaching, such as “Lecturing” and “Case Studies” are in the dominant forms of teaching Inclusive design, with “Debates” and “Problem Based Learning” the next most popular pair of approaches. These four techniques are certainly appropriate approaches for teaching Inclusive Design, but since the topic is so diverse and wide-spanning, there may be some benefit in exploring how other disciplines present Inclusive Design content.

We asked respondents **in within which disciplines is Inclusive Design taught with reference to the European Research Council's Peer Evaluation (PE) panel classifications of Computer Science (PE6) areas.**

- **PE6_1:** Computer architecture, pervasive computing, ubiquitous computing
- **PE6_2:** Computer systems, parallel/distributed systems, sensor networks, embedded systems, cyber-physical systems
- **PE6_3:** Software engineering, operating systems, computer languages
- **PE6_4:** Theoretical computer science, formal methods, and quantum computing
- **PE6_5:** Cryptology, security, privacy, quantum crypto
- **PE6_6:** Algorithms, distributed, parallel and network algorithms, algorithmic game theory
- **PE6_7:** Artificial intelligence, intelligent systems, multi agent systems
- **PE6_8:** Computer graphics, computer vision, multi-media, computer games
- **PE6_9:** Human computer interaction and interface, visualization and natural language processing
- **PE6_10:** Web and information systems, database systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion
- **PE6_11:** Machine learning, statistical data processing and applications using signal processing (e.g. speech, image, video)
- **PE6_12:** Scientific computing, simulation and modelling tools
- **PE6_13:** Bioinformatics, biocomputing, and DNA and molecular computation.

The data reveal a mixed scenery. For example, Software Engineering and Human-Computer Interaction received a strong "Yes" response, indicating that Inclusive Design principles are well integrated in these fields. On the other hand, areas like Cryptology, Scientific Computing, and Bioinformatics had very few "Yes" responses, suggesting that Inclusive Design is not commonly taught or considered in these subjects.

Within which disciplines is Inclusive Design taught?

■ Yes ■ No ■ I don't know

Chart: Inclusion4EU • Created with Datawrapper

While the "No" responses highlight gaps in fields like Parallel/Distributed Systems and Theoretical Computer Science, the more significant finding is the **overwhelming number of "I don't know" responses**. Across many categories - such as Bioinformatics, Machine Computer notable uncertainty, with Systems - there is over Learning, and half of respondents unsure whether Inclusive Design is part of the curriculum in these areas.

This high level of uncertainty highlights a broader issue of awareness, as many respondents are simply unaware of whether Inclusive Design is being taught in their respective fields. This suggests the need for better communication and emphasis on Inclusive Design within informatics education to bridge this knowledge gap.

Understanding the extent to which **key topics related to Inclusive Design are taught is crucial for assessing the effectiveness of educational programs in this field**. By examining various subjects, we can identify which areas are emphasized and which may be overlooked. This exploration not only highlights the commitment of institutions to inclusive

practices but also reveals potential gaps in the curriculum that could affect students' preparedness to address diverse needs in design and technology.

The responses to the question about the extent to which various topics related to Inclusive Design are taught reveal significant trends. The most common type of inclusive content delivered relates to Accessibility Guidelines and Compliance, with 40% of respondents indicating it is taught regularly. Ethics and Web/Mobile Accessibility also feature prominently, with 16% and 18% indicating these topics are taught often. In contrast, areas like Social and Cultural Studies and Legal Regulation and Legislation are far less likely to be included in the curriculum, with 32% and 20% of respondents unsure if they are taught.

These findings indicate that while **foundational topics such as Accessibility Guidelines and Compliance are well addressed** in Inclusive Design education, other important subjects like Social and Cultural Studies receive significantly less attention. This disparity highlights a potential gap in the curriculum that could impede a comprehensive understanding of Inclusive Design.

As far as you know, to what extent are the following topics related to Inclusive Design are taught?

Never
 Sometimes
 Often
 Regularly
 I don't know

Chart: Inclusion4EU • Created with Datawrapper

With regards to **how Inclusive Design is taught**, it is clear that the traditional approaches to teaching, such as lecturing and offering case studies are in the dominant forms of teaching, with debating and problem based learning being the next most popular pair of approaches. These four techniques are certainly appropriate approaches for teaching Inclusive design, but since the topic is so diverse and wide-spanning, there may be some benefit in exploring how other disciplines present Inclusive design content.

How frequently are the following teaching methods used to teach Inclusive Design?

Never
 Sometimes
 Often
 Regularly
 I don't know

Chart: Inclusion4EU • Created with Datawrapper

Similarly and lastly, we investigated **how is Inclusive Design typically assessed**. The top three methods of assessing the students’ understanding of Inclusive design topics are Projects, Essays, and Presentations; three very standard approaches to assessing any Computer Science content. With much lower representation we find Quizzes, Portfolios, and Rubrics; which are slightly more dynamic, and less typical for Computer Science assessment.

How is Inclusive Design assessed?

Chart: Inclusion4EU • Created with Datawrapper

5. Guidelines

Drawing from the insights gathered in our research, we have developed a set of guidelines aimed at addressing the barriers to teaching Inclusive Design in Informatics programmes. These guidelines are intended to provide actionable strategies that institutions can implement to enhance awareness and integration of Inclusive Design principles into their curricula. By focusing on the key areas identified in the data, such as perceptions of importance, staff expertise, and programme structure, these guidelines aim to foster a more inclusive educational environment that better prepares future technology professionals to meet diverse user needs.

- **Teaching and Assessment Content.** Develop off-the-shelf teaching and assessment content that makes it easy for any Computer Science lecturer to deliver lessons on the topic of Inclusive Design, including content that discusses the general impact that computers are having on society, and specifically the inclusion dimension.
- **Software Design Integration.** Develop content that explores the broad area of the design and development of software, and where Inclusive Design fits into that process.
- **Quality Assurance Documentation.** Develop Quality Assurance documentation, such as Module Descriptor documents, to make the incorporation of Inclusive Design into existing programmes as easy as possible.
- **Teaching Approaches.** Develop content that explores approaches to teaching and assessing Inclusive Design, both from within the Computer Science discipline and from other disciplines. Additionally, develop content that addresses ethical inclusion for Computer Science areas explicitly mentioned by respondents and that are regularly featured in the news media. Also, develop content on the importance of Inclusive Design and best practices in Inclusive Design.
- **Accessible Documentation.** Make sure all documentation and online content is accessible and inclusive in both format and in terms of content.
- **Diverse Recruitment.** Focus on the recruitment of more diverse people in all roles within the organisation, including students, researchers, administrators, and managers.
- **Reporting Mechanisms.** Create ways of reporting any challenges people are having in terms of inclusion. Make those reporting mechanisms easy to use and flexible.

- **Support for Inclusive Content Development.** Staff working on developing inclusive content could be given additional time allocation to encourage that kind of activity.
- **Organizational Competitions.** There should be a stronger focus on inclusion using things like organizational competitions focused on this topic to encourage students in this area, as well as raising awareness through social media and other online platforms.
- **Teaching Artefacts.** Develop other teaching artefacts, including creating posters that highlight aspects of Inclusive Design such as accessibility standards, inclusive language, and inclusive methodologies. Also, develop disability simulation tools and tools to teach students about ethnographic studies. In terms of assessment, consider the development of iterative design assignments that span over a number of years of a programme, and authentic assessment scenarios that include end-users.
- **Engagement with Diverse Communities.** People with diverse needs, and organisations that aid them, should be involved in all aspects of the education process, and they should serve as students, lecturers, and researchers. They should also be invited to give guest lectures and collaborate with students on building more inclusive technology solutions, and contribute to the evaluation of assessments.
- **Training Participation.** Staff at all levels of the organisation should be encouraged to participate in training about inclusion and accessibility.

6. Conclusions

The findings of this survey highlight both the progress and challenges surrounding the teaching of Inclusive Design within Informatics programs across Europe. While there is a growing recognition of the importance of Inclusive Design, particularly in response to ethical, legal, and societal demands, the implementation of related curricula remains inconsistent across institutions.

Half of the surveyed institutions have not yet integrated Inclusive Design into their Informatics programs. This gap is attributed to various barriers, such as curriculum overload, lack of staff expertise, and limited awareness of the topic's relevance. Even among institutions that do teach Inclusive Design, the hours devoted to the subject are minimal, with many students receiving less than five hours of instruction per semester.

There is, however, a strong acknowledgment of the need for Inclusive Design education. The survey revealed a consensus on its importance, not only for addressing diverse user needs but also for equipping future professionals with the ethical foundations necessary for responsible technology development. Among institutions that are teaching Inclusive Design, many employ innovative teaching methods, including co-design sessions and engagement with external stakeholders such as disability organizations. These approaches foster a practical understanding of the subject that goes beyond traditional classroom learning.

Nonetheless, significant gaps remain. Many students are not sufficiently exposed to topics such as social and cultural aspects of inclusion, legal regulations, and the broader ethical implications of their work. These areas are crucial for producing well-rounded professionals capable of addressing the complex needs of diverse user populations.

The challenges identified in this study - such as staff availability, lack of awareness, and competing priorities within already busy curricula - underscore the need for systemic change. Institutions should seek to provide more training for educators, develop flexible teaching materials that can be easily integrated into existing courses, and foster collaborations with organizations that support diverse populations.

Looking ahead, the Inclusion4EU project is well-positioned to support these efforts. By continuing to develop resources and guidelines, the project can help institutions overcome the barriers identified in this study and ensure that future generations of Informatics professionals are equipped with the knowledge and skills necessary to design technology that is truly inclusive.

